

LEADERSHIP DUTIES BASED ON LEADERSHIP ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

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ABSTRACT

This article shows how to prepare young people for leadership based on leadership eligibility criteria is not programmable.

Key words : leadership, criterion, team, scientific courage, influence

It is of great importance to form leadership skills and develop management skills in students from the primary grades, based on this principle of thinking and decision-making according to the team, which is characteristic of our mentality .

The word "leader" is used to refer to a person who influences group members and leads to a goal. Sometimes the word "leader" is replaced by the term "leader" in scientific literature. A leader is a member of a social group who can positively influence the thoughts and behavior of people around him, has the ability to perform targeted tasks and has a high personal status. Leadership is a state of relying on the ability formed in a person by analyzing the structure of the group, the system of relationships in it, and showing the ability depending on the opportunity [1-3].

As we noted above, there are many cases of replacing the word "leader" with the term "leader" in various literature. In our opinion, the term "leader" cannot fully express the psychological characteristics of a "leader". The word "leader" is used to refer to a group, a person who influences its members and leads to a goal. Leadership is a state of a person determined by organizing the structure of a group, the system of relations in it. But there are a number of other aspects that represent the quality of a leader, which we cannot analyze only within the framework of the relationship system. In this interpretation, one of the main aspects characteristic of a leader is the ability of a person to act in accordance with the situation. Initiative, harmony and skill in overcoming the difficulty in any problem situation are qualities characteristic of a leader. In a difficult problem-solving situation, a leader is distinguished by his superiority over

others. In our opinion, in the Uzbek language, these two expressions - "leader" and "leader" can fully express the essence of a leader.

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the concept of leader is defined as "Leader" in English as leader-leader, chief, leader. Also: 1. "Leader" is the leader of a political party or organization. 2. A person or team leading in sports competitions; leader, leader: tournament leader, motorcycle race leader [1].

The question of leadership is a question that has its place in every age and is rich in several considerations. In the teachings of our intellectual ancestors, in folk art, there are too many information about just and unjust kings. For example, in the manuscripts of Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Amir Temur, Ulughbek, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Alisher Navoi, Jalaluddin Davani, and others, the personal qualities of leaders (meaning those who occupy high positions) are written in front of them. complex, responsible tasks, instructions for prevention and elimination of certain diseases are presented. In particular, the leader's understanding, wisdom, honesty, philanthropy, honesty, and generosity were emphasized based on scientific and practical examples [4-7].

In our opinion, the word "leader" comes from the desire of a person to lead a group. The expression "Peshqadam" means that a person with certain qualities follows the group, and that the group chooses the path of the person it trusts at its own discretion. The same situation should be used in relation to the expression "leader". This feature of the leader is manifested in his emotional appeal, the virtue of attracting others [8-12].

The problem that we want to study is also aimed at forming some ideas about the personality of the leader, about his influence on the social group and, most importantly, to determine one or another set of characteristics that can make a person a leader. In this way, we try to determine whether these characteristics are hereditary or not, and depending on this (if they are correctable), these characteristics can be formed in another person. At the same time, attention is paid to analyzing the theories put forward by researchers in different periods, to determine what characteristics are concentrated in a leader and which of them rank high, and at the same time, to study programs and trainings that serve to form leadership characteristics in a person. is focused.

In our opinion, an effective class leader should create such an environment in his class team that every student should be able to take part in the tasks and feel that he is participating in this process by using his opportunity in the necessary situation. For this, the team should have students who feel deep responsibility

and are self-confident in solving any task. The child's introduction to collective relations takes place in the system of interpersonal relations with his friends. Other members are the people who enter into collective relations around the child: his parents, siblings and classmates. In the future, the child is formed as an individual, matures into a mature person and finds his place in life, how he enters into collective relations, what psychological climate prevails in the community, how he interacts with his peers. the past is important. At the same time, there are always children in the group who have a universal ability to solve many problematic situations that arise. From this point of view, leadership is largely characterized by the sufficient development of innate abilities of a person. For this reason, the teacher should not forget that the group of students consists of children, and should not ignore the individuality of each student. Loss of psychological contact with students, even for a short period of time, has serious consequences. Therefore, the formation of leadership qualities in each student requires an individual approach to each child from the teacher. In particular, it is appropriate to distribute assignments and tasks according to the internal capabilities of each child, in turn, to give them confidence, encourage them, increase their activity and develop leadership qualities by further strengthening their initiative and organization.

Implementation of the above-mentioned tasks ensures effective functioning of collective relations in the development of leadership qualities. It is also important for the teacher to take into account the following factors when performing such tasks:

- personal example of a pedagogue;
- creating a healthy social environment in the community;
- individual approach to each student.

As a conclusion, it can be said that the implementation and gradual development of leadership qualities in primary grades creates a lot of tasks for the pedagogical process, in which, especially, great tasks are assigned to teachers. This requires a great deal of attention and responsibility from each teacher, as well as the ability to work with a team.

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